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Customer response Analysis in Potato Value Addition: A Success story of Shikarpur Sindh-Pakistan

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Abstract:

The study carries out in Khanpur District Shikarpur. This survey was conducted using a questionnaire, where 40 household heads and 200 customers were sampled and interviewed, the main Objectives of study was to analyse the response of the in Potato Value Addition: A Success story of Shikarpur Sindh. A structural questionnaire was developed for the reliability and validity of data. Farmers were given training at WADO office Khanpur for how to make Potato Powder, Potato Kheer, and Potato chips. It was revealed that Potato value added products training was given to the 50 farmers female/male at Shikarpur.

Key Words: customer Response, Potato Value addition

INTRODUCTION

Over the years, the potato has become an important crop for both farmers and consumers in Pakistan. It is the fourth most important crop by volume of production, and it gives high yields and high returns to farmers. Potato has a high nutritive value and these contribute more protein and iron than other vegetables in the average diet and are also useful sources of thiamine, niacin and several other nutrients including fiber. Almost 86% of potato area and production of Pakistan is achieved from Punjab, i.e., Okara, Sahiwal, Kasur, Sialkot, Sheikhupura, Jhang, Narowal, Pak pattan, Gujranwala, T.T Singh, Khanewal and Lahore. The remaining share is produced by KPK 9%, Baluchistan 4.5%, and Sindh 0.5%.

Pakistan is self-sufficient in potatoes for household consumption and relies for more than 99% on locally produced seed potatoes. Presently, it is estimated that the total annual domestic production amounts to around 2.02 Million MT of which 280000 MT is used as seed and 1.7 Million MT is available for consumption after post-harvest losses. With a population of roughly 150 Million, this accounts to 11 Kg per Capita per annum

Literature Review

The unique position of this vegetable in Poland is not only due to the area of its cultivation but also because of the culinary traditions of Polish people (Leszczyński, 2000). but The harvest amounted to 6.7 million tonnes, and was by about 1.0 million tonnes smaller than in 2014, and in

According to Swanson (2008), the term agricultural extension has changed over times. It is no longer restricted to the emphasis on technology transfer reflected by the Training and Visit (T and V) System but has moved towards broader concepts which include developing the skills and management capacities of farming families (Ovwigbo et al., 2014). Where Other purposes of agricultural and rural extension include marketing extension. Marketing extension (Narayanan 1991) provides information on the post-harvest treatment of specialty crops and provides an important service in countries trading in food crops, Other, different types of marketing information services referred to as «market extension» also exist; these services provide information on variations in commodity prices; knowledge about where to sell some products; information on problems to do with the quality, availability, and prices of inputs, and on the actual level of competition in the markets (Crowder 1997; Shepherd 1997). These market information services should not be confused with marketing

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extension services that aim at improving the preparation and process of moving agricultural goods to market.(FAO, 2001). Extension helped to facilitate the access of farmers, their organisations and other market actors to knowledge and technology, and

MATERIAL AND METHODS

. This survey was conducted using a questionnaire, where 80 household heads and 300 customers were sampled and interviewed, the main Objectives of study was to analyse the response of the in Potato Value Addition: A Success story of Shikarpur Sindh. A structural questionnaire was developed for the reliability and validity of data.

Results:

Variables	Products	1 Strongly Agreed	2 Agreed	3 Neither	4 Disagree	5 Strongly Disagree
Quality	Potato Chips	200	70	30	0	
Taste	Potato Kheer	200	70	20	05	5
Labels & Packages	Potato powder	200	70	20	10	
Taste Difference		250	50	0	0	
Perceive value		200	70	30	0	
Which media channel you prefer		200	70	20	-	10
Electronic		200	70	20	10	
Print		200	70	20	10	
Billboard		200	70	20	10	
Price		200	70	30	0	
Compare to Market Price		250	250	0	10	
How often you used these Products		200	70	20	10	
Innovation		200	70	20	10	
Lack of Financial Facility		200	70	20	10	
		200	70	20	10	

We involved all the local growers who are training and developed their products day before all those hands made products were displayed. I have designed a questionnaire regarding customer’s opinion about our product quality, taste, price, hygiene and their opinion about the homemade products. According to customer test marketing response, 99% of the customers were satisfied with the quality and taste of our products.

We have had a meeting with local shopkeepers as well as entrepreneurs. One of the entrepreneurs is willing to open a store at Kuma, and he will sell growers products, and we also develop a link between market access to the farmers to avoid the middle man.

Conclusions:

The current study focuses on Potato value addition in Khanpur Shikarpur the main objectives of this study that how our project make innovation in different vegetables Khanpur District Shikarpur. We have analysed how to use potato for the betterment and improve livelihood and income for the small farmers. Pakistan is self-sufficient in potatoes for household consumption and relies for more than 98% on locally produced seed potatoes.

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